

FEA-BASED OPTIMIZATION OF AN EFFECTIVE CFRP CONFINEMENT FOR CIRCULAR CFT COLUMNS UNDER CYCLIC LATERAL LOADING

¹MOHAMMAD A. ALHASSAN, ²KHAIRE DIN M. ABDALLA, ³RAJAI Z. AL-ROUSAN, ⁴NIKOS D. LAGAROS

^{1,2,3}Department of Civil Engineering, Jordan University of Science & Technology, Jordan.

⁴Department of Structural Engineering, National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), Greece

E-mail: ¹maalhassan@just.edu.jo, ²abdalla@just.edu.jo, ³rzalarousan@just.edu.jo, ⁴nlagaros@central.ntua.gr

Abstract - Evaluating the structural response of concrete-filled tubular (CFT) steel columns under the combined effects of axial and cyclic lateral loads is a challenge. Accordingly, this study provides new nonlinear finite element analysis (FEA) results of 21 models for CFT columns confined with carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) wrapping at its end. As the end region of the column represents the critical location in terms of the maximum lateral load moment, the intent is to confine the column end to avoid outward local buckling of the CFT column and thus developing high strength, larger net drift and more energy dissipation. The nonlinear FEA models were properly validated with reputable experimental results. After validation, a parametric study was carried out to assess the influence of the number of CFRP layers and axial load level on the CFT column performance. Interesting results were presented in this paper as it was determined that the use of 8 CFRP layers for the evaluated CFT column is the optimum regardless of the axial load level. Also, it was confirmed that the column axial load level significantly affects the CFT steel column behavior under cyclic loading; better behavior as the axial load level increased.

Keywords - CFT Columns, FRP Confinement, Cyclic Lateral Loading, FEA

I. INTRODUCTION

In concrete-filled tubular (CFT) steel columns that are widely used in structural applications, the concern is always about the outward local buckling since the inward local buckling is prevented by the inner concrete. In addition to the axial load, CFT columns in moment resisting or sway frames are subjected to lateral wind or seismic loading that induce moments in the columns; maximum induced moments typically at the column ends. Therefore, the column ends are considered critical locations under the combined effects of axial and lateral loads. In seismic design, it is required that the column is able to experience plastic lateral deformation and sufficient ductility. Many reputable studies were conducted to study the behavior of CFT columns ([1]-[3]). Xiao [4] proposed a confinement technique for CFT columns in which the end portions are confined with fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) wraps to prevent the outward local buckling and allowing the columns to develop higher strength and ductility. The end confinement also improves the inner concrete performance, especially at the highly stressed end regions [4]-[6].

The effectiveness of FRP confinement of CFT steel columns was evaluated afterward in many studies [7–16]). Circular glass FRP confined CFT columns were tested under monotonic axial compression [6] and cyclic axial compression ([17],[18]). However, limited research studies were carried out on the seismic behavior of FRP confined CFT steel columns are limited ([7] - [9],[14]). These studies confirmed

that both circular and square FRP confined CFT steel columns demonstrate excellent seismic resistance.

Testing CFT columns under combined axial and cyclic lateral loading is a challenge since it requires a special setup and testing machine with unique capacities. Availability of sound experimental test results in this regard is considered priceless and can be used to create and validate robust finite element analysis (FEA) simulating the actual ones. With a proper validation, the FEA can be expanded in a parametric study through varying key parameters such as the axial load level and number of FRP layers. Aiming at providing useful and innovative results, this study provides systematic FEA of CFRP-confined CFT circular steel columns under combined axial and lateral cyclic loading.

The FEA models are adequately validated using the results of Yu et al. [19] for a series of large-scale cantilever column tests.

II. MODELING METHODOLOGY

Fig. 1 shows the specimens geometric details and Schematic diagram of experimental test setup [19]. The CFT column is 318 mm in diameter and 1625 mm in height of 1625 mm connected rigidly to a stiff reinforced concrete footing that is 1500 mm long, 1400 mm wide, and 550 mm thick. The steel tube used in all specimens is 3 mm thickness with a diameter to thickness ratio of 106. The confinement at the column end (500 mm) was provided using CFRP jacket to allow for developing a high toughness and ductility.

Fig.1. Schematic diagram of test set-up (dimensions are in mm) [19]

The CFT columns were discretized in ANSYS [20] using 3-D isoperimetric 8-node solid elements as shown in Fig.2. A convergence study was conducted to specify the optimum mesh density. The boundary conditions at the bottom end was constrained as a fixed, whereas the top end was modeled as free. Element Solid65 was selected to model the concrete since it is capable of simulating cracking and crushing. The nonlinear stress-strain diagram used for the concrete in the ANSYS modeling is shown in Fig. 3 with a compressive strength of 36.6 MPa, tensile strength of 3.75 MPa, elastic modulus of 2250 MPa, and Poisson's ratio of 0.20. The Solid65 element can represent one solid material and up to three different types of reinforcement. The concrete was assumed to be isotropic up to cracking and then to undergo plasticity.

Fig.2. Meshing of the CFT specimens with and without CFRP wrapping.

Fig.3. Concrete stress-strain curve

The flexural reinforcement was defined using the smeared reinforcement approach, in which the amount of reinforcement is defined by specifying a volumetric ratio and orientation angles of the mesh.

The SOLID45 element is capable of translating in all directions and used for is used for simulating the loading steel plates and circular steel tube. Linear elastic stress-strain behavior was used with Young's modulus of 203 GPa, yield stress of 271 MPa, an ultimate stress of 353 MPa, and a Poisson's ratio of 0.30. The SOLID46 element was used to simulate the CFRP confinement with an elastic modulus of 237.8 GPa and an ultimate strain of 0.85%, based on a nominal thickness of 0.34 mm [19]. Perfect bond (no slip) was assumed between the concrete and steel tube as well as between the CFRP wrapping and steel tube by merging the coincide nodes.

The column axial load level was applied at first loading step, and then the horizontal load was applied incrementally as displacement-controlled to capture the descending part of the load-displacement curve. To avoid divergence and ensure stable solution, the loading was applied incrementally with many sub-steps within a loading step; Newton-Raphson equilibrium iterative method was employed to obtain the nonlinear solution with a tolerance of 0.001. Calibration of the basic FEA modelling was achieved by using a proper mesh size, rate of loading, and considering materials' nonlinearities.

Fig. 4 shows a good agreement between the load-drift hysteresis results of the FEA and Yu et al. [19] experimental testing for a CFT column confined with six layers of CFRP (its designation in Yu et al. [19] study is LCFT-6C-106-F). Good agreement was observed also between the deformed shapes and failure modes (Fig. 5). Based on that, the calibrated models were used to create a 21 nonlinear FEA models for evaluating the influence of the CFRP number of layers (5 to 10 layers) and the axial load level (0%, 30%, and 50%).

Fig.4. Validation of the FEA results (bottom) with Yu et al. [19] (LCFT-6C-106-F) (top)

III. RESULTS

Table 1 summarizes the results of the 21 nonlinear FEA models that were designated to reflect the studied parameters; i.e. CFT30C5 indicates a model with 30% axial load level and 5 CFRP layers. The maximum horizontal load, net drift, steel strain and CFRP strain were obtained for each model.

The results listed in Table 1 were normalized with respect to specimen CFT0C0 and graphed as shown in Figs. 6 and 7. The results indicates important observations include: 1) as the column axial load increased, the lateral net-drift significantly increased in a non-proportional manner, while the increase in the lateral load capacity was smaller, 2) for a given axial load level, as the number of CFRP layers increased, both the later net-drift and lateral load capacity increased at different rates, 3) The use of less than 5 CFRP layers did not provided a significant performance enhancement, 4)

The performance enhancement with 8 layers of CFRP was nearly comparable with 9 and 10 CFRP layers, 5) the influence of the axial load level and number of CFRP layers on the steel tube maximum strain was minor, and 6) as the number of CFRP layers

increased, the maximum strain experienced by the CFRP was lower. The aforementioned observations indicate that strengthening of CFT circular steel columns with 8 layers of CFRP is very effective and results in measurable performance enhancements in terms of lateral load capacity and net drift.

For each model, the stress contours at the steel tube, core concrete, and CFRP were obtained. Sample stress contours for the cases of no CFRP layers and 8 CFRP layers at an axial load level of 30% are shown in Fig. 8, which demonstrates the most stressed locations especially at the bottom of the column. Sample hysteresis loops were also shown in Fig. 9,

which demonstrates the effectiveness of 8 layers of CFRP for enhancing the CFT column behavior by increasing its lateral load and net drift capacities as well as allowing for higher energy dissipation.

Fig.5. Deformed shapes of the FEA (bottom) and Yu et al. [19] (LCFT-0-106-F) (top)

TABLE I: FEA RESULTS OF ALL MODELS

Specimen Designation	Axial load, %	Number of CFRP layers	Maximum horizontal net drift, mm	Maximum horizontal load, kN	Maximum steel strain, $\square \square$	Maximum CFRP strain, $\square \square$
CFT0C0	0%	0	56.6	87.1	1392	---
CFT0C5		5	63.7	96.0	1432	Rupture
CFT0C6		6	67.1	104.4	1460	7191
CFT0C7		7	72.4	112.5	1496	6814
CFT0C8		8	76.3	118.9	1526	6089
CFT0C9		9	79.2	122.4	1551	5482
CFT0C10		10	81.2	125.7	1560	4953
CFT30C0	30%	0	100.8	100.5	1547	---
CFT30C5		5	110.3	108.4	1571	Rupture
CFT30C6		6	115.0	112.5	1597	7925
CFT30C7		7	123.1	119.5	1622	7503
CFT30C8		8	128.5	124.5	1643	6757
CFT30C9		9	132.1	127.0	1658	6134
CFT30C10		10	134.3	128.0	1663	5597
CFT50C0	50%	0	102.8	102.5	1623	---
CFT50C5		5	115.8	113.9	1648	Rupture
CFT50C6		6	121.9	119.3	1674	8245
CFT50C7		7	131.7	127.8	1700	8093
CFT50C8		8	138.7	134.5	1719	7380
CFT50C9		9	144.0	138.4	1734	6786
CFT50C10		10	147.7	140.8	1745	6269

Note: yielding strain for steel is 1335 $\square \square$ and CFRP ultimate strain is 8500 $\square \square$.

Fig. 6 Effect of the axial load and number of CFRP layers on the maximum horizontal net drift

Fig. 7 Effect of the axial load and number of CFRP layers on the horizontal load capacity

Fig.8 Sample stress contours in the CFRP (left), concrete (middle), and steel tube (left)

Fig. 9. Sample lateral load-net drift hysteresis loops

CONCLUSION

Based on the properly validated 21 nonlinear FEA models, it can be concluded that strengthening of CFT circular steel columns with CFRP layers at its ends results in significant performance enhancement especially in terms of lateral load capacity, net-drift, and energy dissipation. The influence of the column axial load level up to 50% of its axial load capacity is significant and indicates a better performance as the axial load level increases. In the author opinion, the optimum number of CFRP layers is 8 for the evaluated CFT column, and the use of less than 6 layers is not effective. The use of more than 8 layers of CFRP layers did not show measurable additional enhancements compared with 8 CFRP layers.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Part of this work has been supported by the OptArchProject – Optimization Driven Architectural Design of Structures – (H2020-Rise-2015). Their support is highly acknowledged. The authors would like also to thank JUST for its support.

REFERENCES

[1] Y. Ichinohe, T. Matsutani, M. Nakajima, H. Ueda, and K. Takada, “Elasto-plastic behavior of concrete filled steel circular columns,” Proceedings, Third International Conference on Steel-Concrete Composite Structures, Fukuoka, Japan 1991, pp. 131–136.

- [2] L.H. Han and Y.F. Yang, "Cyclic performance of concrete-filled steel CHS columns under flexural loading," *Journal of Construction Steel Research*, 61 (4) (2005) 423–452.
- [3] H.R. Valipour, and S.J. Foster, "Nonlinear static and cyclic analysis of concrete-filled steel columns," *Journal of Construction Steel Research*, 66 (6) (2010) 793–802.
- [4] Y. Xiao, "Applications of FRP composites in concrete columns," *Advances in Structural Engineering* 7 (4) (2004) 335–343.
- [5] J.G. Teng, T. Yu, and D. Fernando, "Strengthening of steel structures with fiber-reinforced polymer composites," *Journal of Construction Steel Research*, 78 (2012) 131–143.
- [6] X.Y. Mao and Y. Xiao, "Seismic behavior of confined square CFT columns," *Engineering Structures*, 28 (10) (2006) 1378–1386.
- [7] Y. Xiao, W.H. He, and K.K. Choi, "Confined concrete-filled tubular columns," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, ASCE 131 (3) (2005) 488–497.
- [8] P. Qin, Y. Xiao, Y. Zhou, and G. Zhang, "Research on CFRP confined circular concrete-filled steel tubular columns subjected to cyclic lateral forces," *Journal of Earthquake Engineering, Engineering Vibrations*, 33 (5) (2013) 190–196.
- [9] W. Gu, C.W. Guan, Y.H. Zhao, and H. Cao, "Experimental study on concentrically-compressed circular concrete filled CFRP-steel composite tubular short columns," *J. Shen-yang Architect. Civil Eng. Univ.* 20 (2) (2004) 118–120 (in Chinese).
- [10] Z. Tao, L.H. Han, and J.P. Zhuang, "Axial loading behavior of CFRP strengthened concrete-filled steel tubular stub columns," *Advances in Structural Engineering* 10 (1) (2007) 37–46.
- [11] Z.B. Wang, Z. Tao, and L.H. Han, "Performance of CFRP-strengthened Concrete Filled Steel Tubes Under Axial Compression," *Proceedings, 10th International Symposium on Structural Engineering for Young Experts*, Hunan University, Changsha, China 2008, pp. 689–694.
- [12] L. Liu and Y.Y. Lu, "Axial bearing capacity of short FRP confined concrete-filled steel tubular columns," *J. Wuhan Univ. Technol. Mater. Sci. Ed.* 25 (3) (2010) 454–458.
- [13] J.W. Park, Y.K. Hong, and S.M. Choi, "Behaviors of concrete filled square steel tubes confined by carbon fiber sheets (CFS) under compression and cyclic loads," *Steel Composite Structures* 10 (2) (2010) 187–205.
- [14] S. Abdalla, F. Abed, and M. Alhamaydeh, "Behaviour of CFSTs and CCFSTs under quasi-static axial compression," *Journal of Construction Steel Research* 90 (2013) 235–244.
- [15] Z.B. Wang, Q. Yu, and Z. Tao, "Behaviour of CFRP externally-reinforced circular CFST members under combined tension and bending," *Journal of Construction Steel Research* 106 (2015) 122–137.
- [16] Y.M. Hu, T. Yu, and J.G. Teng, "FRP-confined circular concrete-filled thin steel tubes under axial compression," *Journal of Composites in Construction* ASCE 15 (5) (2011) 850–860.
- [17] T. Yu, Y.M. Hu, and J.G. Teng, "FRP-confined circular concrete-filled steel tubular columns under cyclic axial compression," *Journal of Construction Steel Research* 94 (2014) 33–48.
- [18] J.G. Teng, Y.M. Hu, and T. Yu, "Stress-strain model for concrete in FRP-confined steel tubular columns," *Engineering Structures* 49 (2013) 156–167.
- [19] T. Yu, Y.M. Hu, and J.G. Teng, "Cyclic lateral response of FRP-confined circular concrete-filled steel tubular columns," *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 124 (2016) 12–22.
- [20] ANSYS 16.0, *Coupled Structural/Thermal Analysis*, (ANSYS Tutorials). Copyright 2001 by University of Alberta.

★ ★ ★